

Navigating the complexities of international data transfer laws for health data research - insights from brain health projects

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Abstract

Dementia is a significant and increasingly urgent global health challenge, estimated to directly affect 153 million by 2050.¹ Advancing our understanding of dementia and developing effective treatments and preventive strategies depends on secure, trustworthy access to high-quality health data. However, international data sharing remains difficult due to complex legal frameworks.

This article draws on projects commissioned by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative¹, which explore collaborative and legally compliant international data sharing. Both projects involve the use of flagship datasets based in the UK (maintained by Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS Foundation Trust and Public Health Scotland.) These datasets hold considerable potential to drive international innovation and discovery in Alzheimer's disease and wider brain health related research, provided they can be accessed securely and lawfully by international research teams.

We explore the legal complexities of cross-border data sharing and the associated challenges. We highlight how emerging privacy-enhancing technologies can help overcome barriers to data sharing, enabling global collaboration while protecting sensitive information. Finally, we demonstrate how the legal hurdles faced by the two pilot studies have been addressed through a combination of technical and governance solutions, fostering a trustworthy environment for international scientific cooperation in the fight against Alzheimer's disease.

¹ Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative, *Accelerating discoveries in Alzheimer's research*, <https://www.alzheimersdata.org/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

Keywords: international data sharing, neurodegeneration, dementia, trusted research environments, privacy, federated data analysis

Introduction

The prevention and treatment of dementia is an urgent global challenge, critical for the wellbeing of ageing populations. Worldwide, dementia directly affects an estimated 57 million people, with that number projected to reach 153 million by 2050.¹ the number of people with dementia is predicted to grow to 153 million by 2050.² Accelerated efforts are therefore needed to improve strategies to identify people at risk, reduce the time from drug discovery to treatment, and improve care delivery. Trustworthy access to large-scale, international, diverse, health and health-relevant datasets could generate transformative insights to advance prevention and treatment strategies. International collaboration is key to ensuring representative populations are included in dementia research, thereby enhancing data diversity across demographics, data types, and collection methods.

The United Kingdom comprises four nations, each with its own history and specific expertise in data science. The UK's National Health Service (NHS) has unique data resources, as it provides healthcare to almost the entire UK population of 67 million.³ Data held by the NHS is unparalleled in its representativeness, variety of modes of data acquisition (e.g. brain images and scans, blood biomarkers, retinal scans, routine visits), scale, and implicit relevance to healthcare users. Access to these large-scale and multimodal data assets would be transformational for the international dementia research community, who are typically able to access only a small number of highly curated datasets that may not represent the populations they serve.

To fully realise the potential of health data, it is essential to strike a balance between individual rights - particularly the right to privacy - and the societal imperative to enable research that benefits global populations. This tension is especially acute in international dementia research, where diverse legal, ethical, and cultural considerations complicate data access across borders. Enabling trustworthy international access to rich data resources, such as those held in the UK, requires not only legal compliance but also the trust and support of UK patients and the wider public. Meaningful public and patient involvement and engagement (PPIE) in research design is therefore fundamental: it

² Quang Tran, Worldwide dementia cases to triple by 2050 to over 150 million people, <https://www.alzheimersresearchuk.org/news/worldwide-dementia-cases-to-triple-by-2050-to-over-150-million/>, (accessed 24 April 2025).

³ Cathie Sudlow, *Uniting the UK's Health Data: A Huge Opportunity for Society*, <https://zenodo.org/records/13353747> (Accessed: June 18, 2025).

provides assurance that individual privacy is protected while data is used safely and securely for collective benefit, fostering trust not only among participants but within the population as a whole. Although not the central focus of this article, this foundation of public trust underpins all that follows.

The laws governing international data transfers are complex and often inflexible in their application. This article focuses on the UK legal framework that must be navigated to enable international access to UK data - a landscape that is rapidly evolving. The most relevant legislation is the UK General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which derives from its EU counterpart and is broadly consistent in application.⁴ We focus on two key dimensions of data protection: anonymisation and international data transfers. When data is truly anonymous, it falls outside the scope of data protection legislation. Accordingly, we explore how anonymity is defined for research purposes and highlight recent developments in both UK and EU regulatory frameworks. In contrast, pseudonymous data remains within the remit of the UK GDPR, often posing significant challenges for international research collaborations due to the complexity of legal compliance for cross-border access and sharing.

Even where lawful mechanisms exist for transferring personal data internationally, implementation can be difficult. The required safeguards are often resource-intensive and demand specialist expertise. This article clarifies what constitutes an international data transfer under UK law and outlines the measures necessary to ensure both legal compliance and a trustworthy research environment.

The Data Pilots Project - a two-year initiative supported by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative - aims to showcase legally compliant approaches for advancing international collaboration in brain health data science. From the outset, international data access was recognised as a significant legal hurdle. To address this, the project has employed a suite of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) to facilitate its pilot studies. Increasingly, data science is conducted within Trusted Research Environments (TREs, also known as Secure Data Environments or SDEs), which are secure computing platforms that allow authorised researchers to analyse data in situ. PETs complement these environments by enabling international collaboration without the need for physical data transfers.

This article examines the benefits and limitations of PETs, using the Data Pilots as illustrative case studies to show how these tools enable collaboration within a complex legal landscape. We outline how these technologies are being applied in practice throughout the project.

⁴ The Information Commissioner's Office, *The UK GDPR*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-and-the-eu/data-protection-and-the-eu-in-detail/the-uk-gdpr/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

In summary, the Data Pilots Project highlights the legal challenges researchers face when conducting global health data research and demonstrates how technology can help overcome these barriers. It has also underscored the urgent need for clear, adaptive laws and policies that evolve alongside technological innovation to fully unlock the potential of health data for international scientific progress.

Legal Analysis: Examination of relevant laws

The Legal Landscape for Health Data Research

Health data constitute personal data of a highly sensitive nature and are subject to strict regulatory oversight. In the research context, it is essential to uphold privacy, confidentiality, trustworthiness, and legal compliance. Researchers must navigate a complex legal landscape that includes data protection legislation, the common law duty of confidentiality, human rights laws, and ethical obligations related to data collected from human participants. This article focuses primarily on data protection laws, as these impose the most significant restrictions on international data transfers.

Post-Brexit, the UK has largely retained the EU's data protection framework through the UK GDPR⁵ and Data Protection Act 2018⁶, which afford a high level of protection and place restrictions on international data transfers and access. The UK recently introduced new legislation, the Data (Use and Access) Act, which entered into law on 19 June 2025.⁷ This Act introduces the first changes to UK GDPR since Brexit, though many provisions are not yet in force and the current legal framework continues to present barriers to international sharing of personal data. Where relevant, this article highlights future changes arising from the new Act. The Information Commissioner's Office (ICO)⁸ publishes guidance and practical recommendations to support compliance with data protection laws, and new guidance implementing the relevant provisions is expected to clarify practical changes to international data sharing in research contexts.

⁵ The GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of Personal Data and on the free movement of such data) forms part of the law of England and Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland by virtue of section 3 of the European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018 and as amended by the Data Protection, Privacy and Electronic Communications (Amendments etc) (EU Exit) Regulations 2019 and Data Protection Act 2018, as amended by the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025.

⁶ Data Protection Act 2018

⁷ UK Parliament, *Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 Stages - Parliamentary Bills - UK Parliament*, <https://bills.parliament.uk/bills/3825/stages> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

⁸ The Information Commissioner's Office, *Home*, <https://ico.org.uk/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

The Common Law Duty of Confidentiality

The Common Law Duty of Confidentiality (CLDC) derives from common law and is founded on the principle that information should not be used or disclosed except in ways understood by the person who disclosed it or with their subsequent permission.⁹ A duty of confidence arises in the health and medical context, and information obtained must be treated as confidential.¹⁰

Disclosures are lawful under certain circumstances: where there is a legal obligation to disclose (e.g., a court order), where consent has been given, or if the data is anonymised (since it is no longer confidential). The CLDC operates differently across the UK. Legislation such as the Health Service (Control of Patient Information) Regulations 2002¹¹ enables the duty of confidentiality to be set aside under specific conditions, provided the disclosure has the relevant regulatory approval. The law of confidence is a consideration for all research involving confidential patient information, irrespective of whether the research involves data transfers.

Understanding Personal Data and Anonymisation

Data protection laws are designed to safeguard individual privacy and set out principles and obligations governing the lawful processing of personal data. Personal data is any data relating to an identified or identifiable living person. Truly anonymised data falls outside the remit of data protection laws, as it cannot be traced or linked back to the individual.

There exists a spectrum of identifiability, with personal data on one end and anonymous data on the other. In between lies pseudonymised data, where direct identifiers are removed but additional information can still be used to re-identify individuals. Determining whether data is truly anonymous or pseudonymous can be legally and technically complex. This distinction is central to assessing the applicability of data protection legislation and the permissible scope of data sharing in research. Data protection law does not specify how you determine whether the anonymous information you release is likely to result in the identification of a person. This is known as the motivated intruder test, and it asks if a determined person can re-identify a specific individual in the data. It requires an

⁹ NHS England, *Section 2: The common law of confidentiality and consent*, <https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/looking-after-information/data-security-and-information-governance/codes-of-practice-for-handling-information-in-health-and-care/a-guide-to-confidentiality-in-health-and-social-care/hscic-guide-to-confidentiality-references/section-2> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

¹⁰ The UK Caldicott Guardian Council, *The common law duty of confidentiality*, <https://www.ukcgc.uk/duty-of-confidentiality> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

¹¹ Health Service (Control of Patient Information) Regulations 2002

examination of all practical steps and means that a determined person may use to re-identify individuals.¹²

The "Reasonably Likely" Test for Anonymisation

The ICO recently published updated guidance on anonymisation,¹³ clarifying that data is anonymous if the risk of re-identification is sufficiently remote. This determination relies on the "reasonably likely" test, a concept rooted in data protection law and affirmed by EU courts. The test has two components: first, whether the organisation holding the data has the means that are reasonably likely to identify individuals; and second, whether any other party accessing the data has such means.¹⁴

UK GDPR reinforces this principle, stating that to determine whether a person is identifiable, one must consider all means reasonably likely to be used - such as "singling out" either by the data controller or another party - to identify the individual directly or indirectly. The ICO's guidance introduces a flexible, context-based approach to anonymisation, recognising that identifiability depends not only on the data itself but also on the environment in which it is accessed. This position aligns with recent rulings by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), which support a nuanced, risk-based interpretation of anonymisation standards.¹⁵

Benefits and Limitations of Anonymisation

Where data has been anonymised, for example, by aggregation into ranges such that no individual can be identified, there are no restrictions on international transfers under data protection laws, as the data is no longer considered personal data and therefore falls outside the scope of UK GDPR. Anonymisation thus provides a pathway for international collaboration without the legal constraints imposed by data protection legislation.

Technologies are available that assist with dataset anonymisation by masking or aggregating data to ensure individuals cannot be identified, either directly or indirectly. For example, the Pandemic Respiratory Infection Emergency System Triage (PRIEST) system utilised and shared anonymised data

¹² The Information Commissioner's Office, *How do we ensure anonymisation is effective?*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/how-do-we-ensure-anonymisation-is-effective/#motivatedintruder> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

¹³ The Information Commissioner's Office, *Anonymisation*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

¹⁴ The Information Commissioner's Office, *How do we ensure anonymisation is effective?* <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/how-do-we-ensure-anonymisation-is-effective/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

¹⁵ European Data Protection Supervisor v Single Resolution Board (2025) Case C-413/23

to enhance decision-making in emergency responses to respiratory infections such as COVID-19.¹⁶ By aggregating and anonymising patient data from various healthcare settings in the UK and internationally, PRIEST allowed healthcare professionals to validate trends and outcomes based on demographic information, clinical symptoms, and treatment responses, enabling public health researchers to identify risk factors, monitor disease spread, and evaluate intervention effectiveness.

However, while anonymised data can still support reasonable scientific conclusions, it significantly limits the range of research that can be conducted. Individual-level prediction is generally not possible, as important research insights may be lost, and researchers are unable to account for the unique characteristics of individuals within the dataset. Researchers frequently seek to undertake longitudinal analysis, which relies on the ability to link data over time for the same individuals. This becomes more challenging when data is fully anonymised for sharing purposes, as anonymisation requires the removal of any means of re-identification, including keys that would allow tracking individuals across different time points. The inability to retain such linkage undermines efforts to study long-term patterns, outcomes or changes at the individual level, underscoring the broader challenge of balancing privacy protection with the need to preserve data utility in research.

What Constitutes an International Data Transfer?

Data protection laws impose restrictions on international "transfers" of personal data. There is no explicit definition of an international data transfer in relevant legislation; however, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) guidance¹⁷ sets out three criteria that define a transfer.¹⁸ First, the data exporter (who can be a data controller or processor) is subject to GDPR. Second, the data exporter discloses by transmission or otherwise makes personal data available to another person. Third, the data importer (or recipient, who again can be a controller or processor) is in a third country¹⁹ (i.e., outside the UK) or is an international organisation. This test is closely mirrored in the ICO's guidance on "restricted transfers," which apply when personal data is transferred outside the UK.²⁰

¹⁶ Ben Thomas et al., *Prognostic accuracy of emergency department triage tools for adults with suspected COVID-19: the PRIEST observational cohort study*. EMJ, (2021) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34083427/>

¹⁷ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 05/2012 On Interplay between application of Article 2 and the provisions of international transfer as per Chapter V of the GDPR Adopted on 14 February 2023*, https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2023-02/edpb_guidelines_05-2021_interplay_between_the_application_of_art3-chapter_v_of_the_gdpr_v2_en_0.pdf (accessed 24 April 2025)

¹⁸ As described in Figure 1.

¹⁹ A third country is a country or territory outside the UK.

²⁰ The Information Commissioner's Office, *A guide to international transfers*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/international-transfers/international-transfers-a-guide/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

EDPB guidance is not legally binding or directly enforceable by courts; however, it influences consistency of approaches to GDPR across Europe. Post-Brexit, the guidelines are no longer directly relevant to the UK regime, though the UK's ICO notes that they give useful guidance. ICO guidance is not legally binding in the UK; however, it is a clear indicator of how the law is applied and is taken into account when enforcement is considered.

Figure 1. The three criteria of international data transfers. Figure description: This graphic portrays three icons in tiles stacked horizontal, which show the three criteria that define an international data transfer. Next to each tile the criteria is written: 1. Exporter (Controller/Processor) subject to GDPR, 2. Exporter discloses by transmission or otherwise makes personal data available to another, 3. Importer is a third country or is an international organisation.

The second criterion warrants further consideration: what qualifies as data being disclosed or made available? Relevant examples include creating accounts, granting access rights to existing accounts, or allowing requests for remote access. This makes clear that a transfer includes personal data that may only be displayed on screen (e.g., for troubleshooting or administrative purposes). Use of cloud platform storage outside the UK is also considered a transfer of personal data, provided other criteria are met.

Trusted Research Environments and Data Transfers

Following these examples, access to personal data within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) from outside the UK does constitute a data "transfer". Whilst TREs offer several safeguards and risk mitigation measures, a data transfer still takes place under the law if the data is accessed by an

individual physically located outside the UK. The ICO notes that making data available to another entity through remote access constitutes an international data transfer.²¹

Navigating International Data Access: Legal Frameworks

The legal framework governing international data sharing is generally dictated by the location of the data subject. In many cases, this corresponds to the jurisdiction where the data is hosted. For example, data collected by the NHS in England falls under English law, including the UK GDPR and other applicable regulations.

When personal data is transferred to a third country, UK GDPR currently requires that the receiving jurisdiction provides a level of protection that is essentially equivalent to that of the UK. These requirements can make international research collaboration difficult and have, in some cases, prevented projects such as those supported by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative Data Pilots. The Data Pilots Project has sought to address these challenges by combining legal compliance with technical safeguards. The use of TREs combined with federated analysis helps mitigate risks and enable secure, trustworthy access to data. This approach seeks to balance the advancement of scientific research with the need to protect individual privacy.

This article focuses on the legal obligations of UK-based researchers and data custodians who wish to share data with international collaborators. While the emphasis is on UK law, similar challenges exist across the EU, where data protection regulations remain broadly aligned and impose comparable constraints on cross-border data sharing.

The Data (Use and Access) Act 2025: A Shifting Legal Threshold

The Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 introduces reforms aimed at streamlining international transfers. Under previous UK and EU GDPR standards, transfers were permitted only if the receiving country offered an essentially equivalent level of protection. The new UK law modifies this test: transfers may proceed if the data exporter, acting reasonably and proportionately, determines that the protection for data subjects is "not materially lower" than that provided under UK law. The Bill became law on 19 June 2025; certain provisions commenced immediately, while key data protection rules are due to come into force before year end. The majority of provisions require secondary legislation to be implemented, which will provide more detailed provisions and contain practical measures that enable the law to be operational and enforceable.

²¹ The Information Commissioner's Office, *A guide to international transfers*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/international-transfers/international-transfers-a-guide/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

This marks a shift in the legal threshold, but its practical implications remain uncertain. In January 2026, the ICO updated its guidance on international transfers including the new “not materially lower” protection test. Importantly, the core structures of the UK's data protection regime - such as adequacy decisions and appropriate safeguards - remain intact under the new Act.

Adequacy Status

Some countries and territories have been granted adequacy status,²² meaning their legal frameworks provide an adequate level of protection for personal data. This designation allows personal data to flow freely between the UK or EU and those jurisdictions without the need for additional safeguards. However, some adequacy decisions are partial, applying only to specific types of organisations. For example, Canada's adequacy status applies solely to commercial entities.

Currently, adequacy arrangements between the UK and EU remain closely aligned. The European Commission oversees adequacy decisions under EU GDPR, while the UK government manages them under UK law. This alignment may diverge as the UK's new Data Use and Access Act 2025 comes into force. The EU has recognised the UK as providing adequate protection for personal data, and the UK has reciprocated by recognising EEA member states and EU institutions as adequate. The EU's adequacy decision for the UK is set to expire in December 2025, at which point it will be reassessed in light of the new UK legislation.

Transfers to Non-Adequate Countries

Where it is necessary to transfer personal data to a non-adequate country for research, Article 46 of UK GDPR lays out appropriate transfer mechanisms, including Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs), the ICO's International Data Transfer Agreement (IDTA), and Binding Corporate Rules (BCRs). These are equivalent to the standards under EU GDPR. BCRs are designed for transfers within a corporate group and are unlikely to apply to research. When relying on these mechanisms to transfer personal data to countries outside of the EEA and UK that are not on the adequacy list, the Data Controller must also complete a Transfer Risk Assessment (TRA) and implement appropriate safeguards provided for under UK GDPR.

Transfer Risk Assessment

A TRA is a complex process involving individual evaluation of the legal regime that applies to the recipient and any personal data they receive. This means the transferring party needs to assess the local laws in the area where the recipient is physically located. Currently, when carrying out a TRA,

²² | Information Commissioner's Office, *A guide to international transfers*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/international-transfers/international-transfers-a-guide/>, (Accessed: 28 October 2025)

the exporter is required to consider whether the laws allowing access to personal data by law enforcement and national security bodies are "essentially equivalent" to those in the EEA and UK - a test that few countries meet. This test will change in the UK once the provisions of the Data (Use and Access) Act regarding international transfers are in force; the standard will change from "essentially equivalent" to "not materially lower."

If this test is not met, then the exporter must either not transfer the data or must put in place additional technical measures to protect personal data. Such measures typically include ensuring that the importer does not have access to personal data in plaintext or only has access to pseudonymised data (this is something TREs can assist with).

Standard Contractual Clauses and Practical Challenges

Once the TRA and any mitigating measures are in place, the organisations still need to ensure additional appropriate safeguards for the data. Most commonly (historically in the UK and currently in the EU), SCCs are used—model contracts that organisations can voluntarily use to demonstrate their data protection compliance. These clauses cannot be changed or amended in any way and enforce contractual obligations upon the data exporter and importer as well as granting protections to data subjects.

SCCs are a common mechanism that enable data sharing with a country not on the adequacy list, but they are often not fit for purpose in a health research context or contain provisions not acceptable to public bodies outside the UK and EEA due to conflicts with local laws or practice. For example, the SCCs require the Data Exporter's courts to have jurisdiction where the data derives from, whereas US educational institutions in certain states (e.g., Texas) are unable to sign contracts with a foreign law jurisdiction clause due to state laws. The requirement to put SCCs in place can therefore cause delays or even prevent research projects from taking place in some circumstances.

It is also possible to use legally binding and enforceable instruments or administrative arrangements between public authorities or bodies which would ensure appropriate safeguards are in place.²³ However, these would typically be discussed with, or approved by, data protection authorities, such as the UK's ICO, which often makes this impractical in practice, as it would be a case-by-case bespoke solution.

²³ The Information Commissioner's Office, *A guide to international transfers*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/international-transfers/international-transfers-a-guide/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

The International Data Transfer Agreement (IDTA)

The ICO has developed the International Data Transfer Agreement (IDTA), which can facilitate international transfers of personal data and can be used as an alternative to the SCCs in the UK. These are UK-specific clauses used when UK organisations are transferring data outside the UK. The IDTA has similar issues to the SCCs in that the relevant UK law is required as the governing law for the agreement.

Consent as a Transfer Mechanism

Organisations can also transfer personal data if the individual has given explicit consent to the transfer, or if an exception applies. Consent under data protection law must be specific, informed, and based on a clear understanding of the particular transfer. This presents practical challenges, as data sharing opportunities often arise long after the data is initially collected. It must also be freely given, which can be problematic in situations involving a power imbalance, or where individuals may face negative consequences for refusing or withdrawing consent.

For these reasons, consent can only be relied upon to facilitate international data transfers in limited circumstances, specifically where the details of the transfer are known at the outset. Crucially, if an individual declines to provide consent, the transfer cannot proceed. This approach is typically impractical for large datasets, where future data sharing opportunities may not be foreseeable at the time of collection.

In the context of dementia research, additional challenges arise. Dementia is predominantly a condition associated with older age, and in cases involving secondary use of retrospective data, many participants may lack the capacity to provide fully informed consent or may be deceased. These factors further complicate the use of consent as a lawful basis for international data sharing in such research settings.

Emerging Technology Solutions

Technology is developing rapidly (e.g. accelerated development of AI), and it is shifting the scientific landscape and our approach to data sharing and access. Historically, data science research would rely on sending raw data directly to another party for their own analysis. We now have a multitude of options, some of which we explore below, that can enable swifter and more secure data access. Some of these emerging technologies can assist in ensuring legally compliant international data transfers. The current governing laws and regulations, however, do not fully consider the capabilities offered by some fast-evolving technologies that are used in an international context to facilitate research.

Introduction to PETs

Privacy enhancing technologies (PETs) encompass a range of environments and methods that promote privacy.²⁴ PETs are technologies which facilitate the analysis of data and enable new findings without granting unrestricted access to the data.²⁵ According to the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)²⁶, PETs include software and hardware solutions, systems and processes designed to achieve specific privacy or data protection functionalities or to protect against privacy risks. There is no single definition or classification of the different types of PETs. However, they can be divided into four main categories: data obfuscation (e.g. anonymisation or synthetic data); encrypted data processing (e.g. homomorphic encryption); federated and distributed analytics; and data accountability tools.²⁷ A specific PET can belong in multiple categories and can be utilised independently or in conjunction with others.

PETs work by reducing the risk of personal data breaches by applying the data minimisation principles, enhancing data security, and protecting privacy.²⁸ These technologies are crucial, especially in research settings, as they promote collaboration while facilitating access to personal data in a compliant manner that permits reproducibility and transparency.

The ICO has explicit guidance on PETs, noting they embody many core data protection principles and adhere to the concept of “data protection by design”.²⁹ PETs can assist in rendering data anonymous; however, their use does not automatically render data anonymous, and researchers need to assess anonymisation per the tests described earlier. Many PETs simply aim to enhance privacy and protect the data being processed, rather than anonymise it. Hence, many PET use cases still involve personal data and require compliance with data protection obligations.

²⁴ ENISA European Union Agency for Cyber Security, (2016), *Readiness Analysis for the Adoption and Evolution of Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/pets> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

²⁵ The Royal Society, *From privacy to partnership*, (2023) <https://royalsociety.org/-/media/policy/projects/privacy-enhancing-technologies/from-privacy-to-partnership.pdf>. (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

²⁶ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), *Who we are*, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/about-enisa/who-we-are> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

²⁷ OECD, *Emerging privacy-enhancing technologies (EN)*, (Mar. 3, 2023), https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2023/03/emerging-privacy-enhancing-technologies_a6bdf3cb/bf121be4-en.pdf. (Accessed: 29 October 2025).

²⁸ ICO, *How can PETs help with data protection compliance?*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/privacy-enhancing-technologies/how-can-pets-help-with-data-protection-compliance>. (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

²⁹ ICO, *How can PETs help with data protection compliance?*, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/privacy-enhancing-technologies/how-can-pets-help-with-data-protection-compliance> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

TREs, also known as Secure Data Environments (SDEs), Data Safe Havens or Secure Processing Environments (SPEs), are highly secure computing environments that provide remote access to health data, support the highest standards of information governance, transparency, and security and, importantly, remove the need for data to be physically transferred between different users.^{30,31} TREs operate by providing researchers with a single location to access and analyse data, and have controls in place to prevent data being exported without permission.

The status of data held within a TRE may be personal or anonymous, depending on the context and content of the data itself. Although the use of a TRE in and of itself does not permit international data transfer, it can be an integral part of a compliant international data access solution.

TREs typically adhere to the “Five Safes Framework” which is a structured set of principles that facilitate evaluation of different aspects of a research project to manage access to confidential data.³² This framework ensures safe data (data treated in a manner to protect participant confidentiality), safe people (only approved researchers have access to the TRE), safe projects (only approved research projects in the public good are permitted), safe settings (the TRE acts as a secure setting preventing unauthorised use), and safe outputs (outputs go through an output review process ensuring that any results are non-disclosive). The TRE itself constitutes a safe setting, and other elements are facilitated by the TRE- for example, outputs cannot be downloaded without a mandatory output checking process. Alongside this, other safeguards such as a Data Access Agreement (DAA) are standard practice between TRE user organisations and the TRE host.

The European Health Data Space Regulation, published earlier this year, involves creating a common harmonised framework for the use of health data across the EU.³³ Under this Regulation, the processing of health data will be restricted to SPEs,³⁴ with the certification criteria for SPEs being

³⁰ Tim Hubbard et al., *Trusted Research Environments (TRE) Green Paper*, https://zenodo.org/records/4594704#.YTiCT_eSk2y (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³¹ UK Health Data Research Alliance and NHSX, *Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems*, <https://zenodo.org/records/5767586> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³² Tanvi Desai, Felix Ritchie, Richard Welpton, *Five Safes: designing data access for research*, 1601, UWE Economics Working Paper Series, (2016) <https://www2.uwe.ac.uk/faculties/BBS/Documents/1601.pdf>

³³ European Commission, *European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS)* https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³⁴ Article 50, European Health Data Space (EHDS)

implemented by the European Commission by March 2027.^{35 36} In the UK, TREs can be accredited by a convening body such as the Scottish Safe Haven Network³⁷, NHS England³⁸, and the UK Statistics Authority³⁹. Additionally, TREs can self-evaluate against the Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) specification that aims to standardise the capabilities of TREs.^{40 41}

Figure 2. Infographic detailing the benefits provided by a Trusted Research Environment (TRE)⁴². Figure description: In the centred box titled Trusted Research Environments (TREs) seven benefits of TREs are listed: 1. secure airlock environment 2. configurable tools and services 3. enhanced collaboration 4. single, secure data storage 5. secure remote access 6. scalable computer power 7. enhanced trustworthiness. Arrows connect to the central box with icons and labels showing involved stakeholders: researchers, data managers, data custodians, and public, patients, practitioners.

³⁵European Health Data Space (EHDS), *Updates*, <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³⁶European Health Data Space (EHDS), *Updates*, <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³⁷Scottish Government, *Safe havens: charter*, <https://www.gov.scot/publications/charter-safe-havens-scotland-principles-standards-scottish-safe-haven-network-support-use-data-enable-research-innovation-scotland/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³⁸NHS England, *Secure Data Environments (SDEs)*, <https://transform.england.nhs.uk/key-tools-and-info/data-saves-lives/secure-data-environments/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

³⁹NHS England, *Secure Data Environments (SDEs)*, <https://uksa.statisticsauthority.gov.uk/digitaleconomyact-research-statistics/better-access-to-data-for-research-information-for-processors/list-of-digital-economy-act-accredited-processing-environments/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

⁴⁰Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE), *Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE)*, <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

⁴¹The SATRE specification is currently being revised to strengthen its focus on federation and disclosure control.

⁴²Matt Retford et al *Overview and key considerations for establishing a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) for global health research* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928551>

Federated Analysis / Remote Querying

Federation technology⁴³ can allow computation and analysis to be performed on datasets without requiring a researcher to have direct access to the dataset. This can be done by sending the analysis to a data custodian's TRE, a separate entity, where the computation code can be checked, executed if appropriate, and analysis results are returned to the researcher only after output checking. A federated system can be implemented such that the researcher never directly accesses or receives any personal data, with only high-level counts or other non-disclosive results returned. Output checking is put in place to ensure this is the case. This means no transfer occurs, and data protection laws are not applicable. This type of analysis is often referred to as "federated analysis" or "remote query" and can simplify the process from an approval point of view. It does, however, have the downside of not allowing the researcher to run their own code directly against the data, or directly view or access the data. It can also introduce time delays if the federated analysis results are held in quarantine for long periods by the data custodian.⁴⁴ The Semi Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO) project, as part of DARE UK, is addressing delays in disclosure checking.⁴⁵ For federated analysis to work well, it is also critical that researchers have a high degree of understanding of the data formatting and its constructs (i.e. its metadata - the data about the data). This federated analysis technology is being used by both of the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative Data Pilots.

Other PETs (synthetic data, encryption, etc.)

Synthetic data is artificial data generated from a dataset and emulates the properties of the original dataset.⁴⁶ Synthetic data preserves key statistical properties, such as distributions and correlations, and can range from partially to fully synthetic data. Partially synthetic data typically replaces only the sensitive portions of real-world datasets with artificial values to protect privacy, while fully synthetic data is generated entirely from scratch using predefined rules, models, or simulations and contains

⁴³ Solmaz Eradat Oskou et al., *Developing a Prototype for Federated Analysis to Enhance Privacy and Enable Trustworthy Access to COVID-19 Research Data*, 195 International Journal of Medical Informatics (2025).

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S138650562400371X#ab010>

⁴⁴ Addressing the issue of delay in disclosure checking is being worked on by the Semi Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO) project, as part of DARE UK.

⁴⁵ DARE UK, *SACRO: Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs*, SACRO: Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, <http://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/previous-activities/dare-uk-phase-1-driver-projects/sacro-semi-automated-checking-of-research-outputs/> (accessed 24 October 2025).

⁴⁶ PHG Foundation, *Are synthetic health data 'personal data'?*, <https://www.phgfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Are-synthetic-health-data-%E2%80%98personal-data.pdf> (accessed 24 April 2025).

no original real-world information.^{47,48} Synthetic data may or may not be classified as personal data, depending on a variety of factors including the data itself, the environment, context, nature, and safeguards which governed its creation⁴⁹. The closer the data is to the source data the more likely it is to be considered personal data. Synthetic data is an example of a PET that reduces or removes the likelihood of the individuals whose data is being processed being identified and can uphold the principle of data minimisation by breaking the identifiable connection between the original and derived data.^{50, 51}

Homomorphic encryption⁵² allows computations to be performed on encrypted data without the need to ever decrypt it. Additionally, the computations can also be encrypted. Once outputs are decrypted, they are identical to those that would have been performed on the original unencrypted data. Researchers never have access to the data in unencrypted form and are unable to unencrypt it themselves, making the data anonymised and removing restrictions on international research described above. However, this approach is currently computationally expensive and technically demanding, often requiring significant processing power and time to perform even relatively simple analyses.⁵³ As researchers cannot view or directly inspect the data, there is a real risk of misinterpretation or drawing misleading conclusions, particularly when underlying datasets are not standardised, well- curated or clean. These challenges apply not only to homomorphic encryption but more broadly to any privacy preserving computational approach and as such, these remain an emerging and largely unproven approach in health data research. Overall, careful validation and robust data governance remain essential before large scale adoption.

Secure Multi-Party Computation⁵⁴ shields data to protect individuals' privacy while not affecting the utility and accuracy of the data. It is a protocol that allows multiple parties to process their combined

⁴⁷ Jerome Reiter, *Inference for partially synthetic, public use microdata sets*, 29, *Surv. Methodol.* (2003)

⁴⁸ Trivellore Raghunathan, Jerome Reiter and Donald Rubin, *Multiple imputation for statistical disclosure limitation*, 19, *J. Stat.* (2003)

<https://www.scb.se/contentassets/ca21efb41fee47d293bbee5bf7be7fb3/multiple-imputation-for-statistical-disclosure-limitation.pdf>

⁴⁹ PHG Foundation, *Are synthetic health data 'personal data'?*, <https://www.phgfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Are-synthetic-health-data-%E2%80%98personal-data.pdf> (accessed 24 April 2025).

⁵⁰ Theodora Koksi and Katie Haroon, *Synthetic data in medical research*, *BMJ Medicine* (2022) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36936569/>

⁵¹ Mauro Giuffrè and Dennis L. Shung, *Harnessing the power of synthetic data in healthcare: innovation, application, and privacy*. *npj Digit. Med.* 6, 186 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00927-3>

⁵² Kundan Munjal and Rekha Bhatia, *A systematic review of homomorphic encryption and its contributions in healthcare industry*, *Complex Intell System*, (2022) <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9062639/>

⁵³ Kundan Munjal and Rekha Bhatia, *A systematic review of homomorphic encryption and its contributions in healthcare industry*, *Complex Intell System*, (2022) <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9062639/>

⁵⁴ Chuan Zhao et al., *Secure Multi-Party Computation: Theory, practice and applications*, *Inf. Sci.* (2019) <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0020025518308338>

information without either party needing to disclose the entire data set to another. The data may be anonymised or personal data and, if considered personal data, all relevant data protection laws need to be complied with. There are other PETs available in what is a rapidly evolving space that are not covered as part of this paper.

Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative Data Pilots as case studies showing PETs in practice

Both Data Pilots are using TREs combined with federated analytics to ensure secure and privacy-protecting access to personal data.

The first Data Pilot is a collaboration between Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS Foundation Trust and a United States-based academic institution to investigate the retinal features of neurodegeneration. In this project, retinal scan data is held securely within the Moorfields Secure Data Environment. Alongside this, the research team is employing federated analysis techniques to enable collaborative research without transferring personal data across borders. This approach allows researchers in each country to analyse data from within their own TRE, with only the analytical requests and their subsequent approved outputs being shared across country boundaries. External collaborators do not have direct access to datasets held outside their jurisdiction. Here, federated analysis enables cross-jurisdictional research without requiring personal data to be transferred outside its host country. Furthermore, this project improves “research readiness” of datasets for research related to Alzheimer’s disease internationally and focuses on improving the use of, and access to key datasets. These datasets have been made FAIR⁵⁵ and the study will demonstrate how they can be used by researchers outside of the organisation that is responsible for managing, maintaining and protecting the datasets both within the UK and internationally, and in a safe, trustworthy and legally compliant manner.

The second Data Pilot involves the University of Edinburgh and Public Health Scotland, working in collaboration with their international partners in Finland. This project is investigating if AI-derived retinal features can discriminate between individuals with and without all-cause dementia across datasets located in the UK, enabling the piloting of federated access to this data for collaborators in the United States. This will be followed by an analysis of interocular asymmetry (the difference in retinal nerves between the two eyes of the same individual) in distinguishing vascular dementia from Alzheimer’s disease.

⁵⁵ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. [Mark D. Wilkinson et al., The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 \(2016\)](https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618)
<https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

The research project involves a series of studies, including comparing brain age calculated with computed tomography (CT) scans with brain age calculated with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). These will investigate whether having an “older brain age” increases the chance of dementia, by considering the person’s actual age and prediction of dementia using the scans. The Scottish Medical Imaging dataset, containing over 6 million brain images linked to hospitalisation, medication and death records is resident within the Public Health Scotland (National Safe Haven TRE). This will be analysed in conjunction with the Helsinki University Hospital (HUS)⁵⁶ dataset from Finland via the HUS Academic platform. Federated analytics is also being employed here to facilitate global research in a compliant manner, i.e. a researcher in Finland will create a query their TRE and send it to the National Safe Haven TRE in Scotland. The query will be run in the Scottish National Safe Haven with only high-level non-disclosive outputs (e.g. counts) being returned to the researcher in Finland.

As part of these Data Pilots, the Alzheimer’s Disease Data Initiative has developed the Federated Data Sharing Appliance (FDSA), enabling collaborative Alzheimer’s disease research by providing a federated analysis technology solution for researchers and data custodians. This allows data custodians to maintain control over their data while providing researchers with streamlined capabilities for remote querying and analyses, without direct data access. This approach enables global research collaboration as it allows analysis and questions to be asked about data sets without that data moving or international users directly accessing the data. Further, it promotes data privacy whilst unlocking previously inaccessible datasets and accelerating Alzheimer’s disease research by supporting legally compliant, collaborative efforts across the international scientific community.⁵⁷ The FDSA approach of sending containerised analysis requests using a common application programming interface (API) builds on the pilot projects.

Barriers and Future Directions

The Challenge: Balancing Protection and Access

To enable broader adoption of PETs, it is essential to address both technical and governance barriers.⁵⁸ Data custodians must strike a difficult balance between protecting individual trust and safeguarding the security and integrity of sensitive data, while also improving the utility and usage of

⁵⁶ HUS, *HUS Academic - secure operating environment*, <https://www.hus.fi/en/research-and-education/tutkijan-palvelut/hus-academic-secure-operating-environment> (accessed 24 April 2025).

⁵⁷ Arthur W. Toga et al., *The pursuit of approaches to federate data to accelerate Alzheimer’s disease and related dementia research: GAAIN, DPUK, and ADDI*, *Front. Neuroinform* (2023) <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/neuroinformatics/articles/10.3389/fninf.2023.1175689/full>

⁵⁸ ICO, *Tackling barriers to privacy-enhancing technologies adoption - a PETs project report*, <https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/research-reports-impact-and-evaluation/research-and-reports/technology-and-innovation/tackling-barriers-to-privacy-enhancing-technologies-adoption/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

key datasets for critical research that results in public benefit. Currently, risk-averse approaches often dominate, understandably prioritising data protection, but sometimes at the expense of innovation and collaborative international research opportunities.

The Need for Standardisation

For PET providers to effectively support data custodians in navigating this challenge, consistency and interoperability are essential. This requires open standards, common application programming interfaces (APIs), and standardised governance processes, procedures, and templates. Without such standardisation, each PET must be assessed individually through lengthy, resource-intensive reviews that erode the productivity gains these technologies promise.

Promising examples of standardisation are already emerging. HDR UK and DARE UK's Federated Analytics initiative, which uses the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Task Execution Service (TES) standard for federated solutions, demonstrates how open standards can streamline adoption.⁵⁹ The challenges faced by both Data Pilots reflect this lesson: adopting an open standards-based, repeatable approach is essential for reducing duplication of effort and ensuring sustainable success across multiple projects.

Evolution of regulatory frameworks

Beyond technical and governance challenges, regulatory frameworks must better recognise how emerging technologies reduce risk. Currently, data protection law is applied strictly, often without adequately accounting for the risk mitigation that modern technologies provide.

For example, Transfer Risk Assessments (TRAs) are required for any restricted international transfer to evaluate whether the protections in the receiving jurisdiction are essentially equivalent to UK standards. This assessment is crucial for identifying and mitigating risks. However, current guidance does not fully account for how PETs such as TREs, federated analysis and encryption substantially reduce these risks in practice. When data remains within a secure TRE and is never exported, or when only non-disclosive aggregate results cross borders through federated queries, the risk profile is fundamentally different from traditional data transfers where datasets are sent directly to recipients.

A more nuanced regulatory approach would recognise that PETs can materially reduce the risks that TRAs are designed to assess. Rather than applying a uniform standard regardless of technical

⁵⁹ Health Data Research UK, *Federated Analytics*, <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/research/research-data-infrastructure/federated-analytics/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).
Federated Research, *Adopt Standards. Build Trust. Enable Federation. Accelerate Research*, <https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

safeguards, risk assessments could better account for the protective measures these technologies provide. This would enable proportionate compliance and maintain rigorous assessment, while acknowledging that robust technical controls reduce risks in a meaningful way.

Similarly, updated anonymisation guidance requires risk re-assessment whenever a new party is given access to data. This approach is understandable in the context of traditional data dissemination, where datasets are sent directly to researchers with limited ongoing control. However, in TRE environments - where data never leaves a secure setting, access is tightly controlled through vetting and permissions, and all outputs undergo disclosure checking - the risk of re-identification is substantially mitigated. Current guidance does not fully reflect how these layered safeguards work together to reduce risk, instead treating all access scenarios similarly regardless of the technical and procedural controls in place.

These examples illustrate a broader challenge: laws and regulations designed for traditional data sharing models do not always recognise the risk reduction that emerging technologies provide. As PETs continue to evolve and demonstrate their effectiveness, regulatory guidance should evolve to reflect how these technologies lower risk, enabling more proportionate and evidence-based compliance frameworks.

PETs as Enablers of Compliant Research

Despite these challenges, PETs offer significant promise for advancing international health data research. They help achieve compliance with core data protection principles, particularly data security, minimisation of data movement, and the principle of data minimisation itself. Importantly, they do so by fundamentally reducing the risks associated with data sharing.

Critically, whether data anonymisation alone, a single PET, or a combination of multiple PETs is sufficient depends entirely on the specific circumstances and data involved. There is no one-size-fits-all solution. These technologies can be deployed independently or combined in layered approaches, each with different risk profiles, benefits, and limitations. Traditional data dissemination - sending datasets directly to researchers - offers minimal protection and little ongoing control. In contrast, modern solutions such as TREs, federated analysis, synthetic data, and homomorphic encryption provide robust safeguards that include limiting data access, researcher and project vetting, output checking, technical controls and audit trails, thereby substantially reducing risks.

Careful consideration of these options should be integral to the design phase of any health data research project. When thoughtfully implemented, PETs provide valuable tools to enable

international collaboration whilst protecting data privacy and effectively implementing "data protection by design."

Demonstrating Risk Reduction

For PETs to gain wider acceptance and recognition within regulatory frameworks, there is a need for systematic evidence demonstrating their effectiveness at reducing risk. This includes clear documentation of how specific PETs mitigate identified risks in TRAs, with audit trails and transparency that demonstrate technical controls function as intended. In addition, standardised frameworks could be used to evaluate the risk reduction provided by different PET approaches; and case studies such as the Data Pilots can demonstrate successful, secure international collaboration. Building this evidence base will support the evolution of regulatory guidance and help data custodians make informed, risk-based decisions about deploying PETs to enable international research collaboration.

Future Direction

These technologies hold considerable potential for health researchers seeking trustworthy, legally compliant approaches to international data access. However, realising this potential requires coordinated effort across multiple fronts: continued technical innovation, adoption of open standards, evolution of regulatory frameworks to recognise risk reduction, and education of both data custodians and researchers about available solutions.

Individual research projects have distinct needs, and researchers should work closely with data custodians and legal advisors to assess how these solutions can best enable their scientific objectives while keeping data protected, secure, and legally compliant. The Data Pilots demonstrate that with careful planning, appropriate technology and collaborative approaches, legally compliant international brain health research is not only possible but can be achieved, while substantially reducing risks to data security and privacy. As these approaches mature, become standardised, and an evidence base for their risk reduction capabilities is built, they offer a roadmap for the broader research community to follow.

Discussion & Conclusions

The future of international health data research depends on our ability to harness data across national borders while maintaining the highest standards of privacy and security. This article has demonstrated that privacy enhancing technologies offer a potentially transformative solution, enabling legally compliant, trustworthy international collaboration that can accelerate scientific

discovery and deliver substantial public benefit. The path forward is not singular; researchers must thoughtfully evaluate which technologies - or combination of technologies - best serve their specific research objectives and data environments.

The Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative Data Pilots represent a critical proof of concept. By deploying TREs and federated analytics, these initiatives have successfully made flagship brain health datasets available to international researchers on a secure, legally compliant basis. This achievement demonstrates that the barriers to international dementia research are surmountable. The approaches piloted here offer a blueprint not only for Alzheimer's research but for addressing a broad spectrum of global health challenges. However, these successes also highlight that the methods that work well for these specific use cases will not suit all research contexts. The underlying legal frameworks must evolve to accommodate the full range of emerging technological solutions.

The Imperative for Regulatory Evolution

Current UK data protection frameworks lack the nuance necessary to fully recognise the risk reduction that TREs and other PETs provide. This regulatory rigidity creates unnecessary friction and fails to fully incentivise adoption of technologies that materially enhance data security. Technology evolves rapidly, and regulatory frameworks must keep pace. Laws and guidance that fail to recognise technological advancement risk becoming obstacles to the very research that serves the public good.

The UK's new Data Use and Access Act offers an opportunity for reform. Its provisions aim to simplify international transfers and, importantly, empower the Secretary of State to recognise new transfer mechanisms. This power should be exercised in the context of health research. A new transfer mechanism specifically designed to accommodate TREs - recognising their operational safeguards, current accreditation standards, and demonstrated risk reduction - would maintain rigorous protection while facilitating vital research.

Similarly, standards agreement used (e.g. SCCs or IDTA) require updating for the research context. These were not designed with PETs in mind and create practical obstacles for research collaborations that pose minimal risk due to robust technical controls. An updated research-specific framework could address these limitations while maintaining essential protections.

The Technology Community Must Deliver

PET providers must also deliver on the promise of secure, efficient international collaboration. Too often, new technologies create isolated solutions with unique interfaces, governance requirements, and operational models. Each becomes another silo, requiring data custodians to navigate bespoke assessment processes that negate the efficiency gains these technologies should provide.

The solution lies in standardisation and interoperability. Federated solutions that operate within TREs must converge around common standards: open APIs that enable seamless integration, standardised query packaging that ensures consistency, flexible deployment options that accommodate diverse infrastructure environments, well-defined execution environments that provide predictable behaviour, adherence to recognised technical certifications, robust security management protocols, and consistent information governance frameworks. Only through such standardisation will individual technologies contribute to a coherent, interoperable ecosystem rather than fragmenting the landscape further.

A Call for Collaborative Action

Progress requires partnership. Legislative and regulatory bodies must work closely with technology providers, researchers, and data custodians to develop frameworks that are both protective and proportionate. The Data Pilots show that such collaboration yields tangible results, enabling research that was previously impossible while maintaining public trust and data security.

The stakes could not be higher. Dementia affects millions globally, with numbers projected to reach 153 million by 2050.⁶⁰ Yet research progress remains constrained by our inability to efficiently and legally share data across borders. We have the technological capability to overcome these barriers. What we need now is the regulatory adaptation and ecosystem coordination to unlock that potential at scale. If we succeed, we will not only accelerate breakthroughs in Alzheimer's research but establish a model for addressing every major international health challenge that requires cross-border data collaboration.

Acknowledgements

This work is funded by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative and convened by Health Data Research UK.

The referenced projects use data provided by patients and collected as part of their care and support by Public Health Scotland and Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS Foundation Trust.

The authors wish to recognise these patients for their contribution of the data that made these research projects possible.

⁶⁰ Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative, *Accelerating discoveries in Alzheimer's research*, <https://www.alzheimersdata.org/> (Accessed: 28 September 2025).

Appendix 1 - Technology solutions

Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

The Alzheimer's Disease (AD) Workbench (AD Workbench)

The Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative's mission is to accelerate Alzheimer's disease research by enabling collaborative data sharing and analysis. The Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative's trust-by-design TRE solution is the Alzheimer's disease (AD) Workbench⁶¹. The AD Workbench delivers access to key datasets around the world across public and private sectors using a secure cloud-based data platform and can be instantiated in whichever country required. In this case, the US and Europe. The AD Workbench provides data contributors with flexible data sharing options that preserve their branding and maintains their control and autonomy over the data through configurable data access requests and approval workflows. Along with hosting some datasets centrally in a cloud-based repository, the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative has achieved interoperability with other initiatives such as Dementias Platform UK (DPUK)⁶², European Platform for Neurodegenerative Diseases (EPND)⁶³, Global Alzheimer's Association Interactive Network (GAIN)⁶⁴ and Vivli⁶⁵.

INSIGHT Secure Research Environment (SRE)

INSIGHT, the UK's Health Data Research Hub for Eye Health, provides a Secure Research Environment (SRE) to facilitate secure, ethical, and effective use of sensitive clinical and imaging data by authorised researchers. Also known as a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) or Data Safe Haven, the SRE is a highly secure, cloud-based platform that supports data-driven research while upholding strict standards of governance, patient confidentiality, and regulatory compliance.

Access to the SRE is granted only after a Data Use Agreement (DUA) is established between the researcher's institution and the data controller, Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS Foundation Trust. This agreement governs all aspects of data access, use, and export. Once approved, researchers are provided with customised virtual machines pre-configured with the necessary software tools to conduct their analyses entirely within the secure environment.

⁶¹ Alzheimer's disease Workbench, *Alzheimer's disease data initiative*, <https://www.alzheimersdata.org/> (Accessed: 28 October 2025).

⁶² Sarah Bauermeister et al., *The dementias platform UK (DPUK) data portal*, *Eur. J. Epidemiol* (2020) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32328990/>

⁶³ Scott C Neu et al., *Sharing data in the global alzheimer's association interactive network*, *Front. Neurol*, (2016) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36530625/>

⁶⁴ Scott C Neu et al., *Sharing data in the global alzheimer's association interactive network*, *Front. Neurol*, (2016) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36530625/>

⁶⁵ Vivli, *A global clinical research data sharing platform*. <https://vivli.org> (Accessed: 28 October 2025)

Crucially, raw data remains within the SRE at all times. Only pre-approved results may be exported, and only after review and authorisation by the data custodian. This ensures that all research outputs are aligned with ethical and legal standards.

INSIGHT's SRE framework enables high-impact research in eye health and related fields, while maintaining public trust through rigorous controls and oversight. In certain cases, and subject to appropriate governance approvals, INSIGHT may also offer alternative data access mechanisms, such as secure data egress. The SRE supports safe and innovative research while protecting individual privacy and ensuring full compliance with all relevant legal, ethical, and technical requirements.

Scottish National Safe Haven (NSH)

The National Safe Haven (NSH), operated by Public Health Scotland (PHS) through the Electronic Data Research and Innovation Service (eDRIS), provides a secure, privacy-preserving environment for the analysis of health and social care data in Scotland. It enables accredited researchers to access linked, de-identified datasets for projects that have received all necessary approvals, supporting high-quality, impactful research while safeguarding individual confidentiality.

The NSH is built on a robust technical infrastructure and governance model. Researchers access data via a secure Virtual Desktop Infrastructure (VDI), which offers a suite of analytical tools within a controlled environment. Access is granted only after comprehensive review and approval processes, including data controller permissions, ethics approvals, and formal data access agreements. The platform is ISO 27001 certified and fully compliant with Scottish and UK data protection laws.

All data remain within the NSH throughout the research process. Researchers are not permitted to download raw data; only aggregate results that have passed strict disclosure control procedures may be exported. This ensures that personal data is protected across the research lifecycle.

By providing secure access to high-quality, linked datasets, the NSH enables research that informs public health policy and improves outcomes across Scotland and beyond. Its combination of technical security, rigorous governance, and user support ensures both the integrity of research and the trust of data subjects.

Federated Technology

See Federated Data Sharing Appliance (FDSA) information on page 19 of this article.